

System Overview

The reinforcement learning (RL) task at hand involves optimizing traffic signal control (TSC) at a signalized intersection with four access roads. The goal is to manage traffic flow efficiently by dynamically adjusting traffic signal phases to minimize congestion, delays, and conflicts. The environment consists of a four-legged intersection with six lanes in each direction (north, west, south, and east). Vehicles follow standard movement rules: turning left from the leftmost lane, proceeding straight from the middle or rightmost lane, and turning right from the rightmost lane.

The action space consists of four predefined traffic signal phases:

1. **WEG (West-East Green)** – Green light for straight and right-turning vehicles in the W-E direction.
2. **WELG (West-East Left Green)** – Green light for left-turning vehicles in the W-E direction.
3. **NSG (North-South Green)** – Green light for straight and right-turning vehicles in the N-S direction.
4. **NSLG (North-South Left Green)** – Green light for left-turning vehicles in the N-S direction.

Each phase lasts a minimum of 10 seconds, with a mandatory 4-second yellow light during transitions.

The simulation is based on real-world data collected from an intersection in Changsha City, China and operates within the SUMO traffic simulation environment using the TRACI module to interact with real-time traffic states. The system will be deployed in the same intersection as the simulation data was collected from.

Your Task

You will contribute to designing the system with a focus on **[OBJECTIVE]**. To do this, you will complete the following steps:

Steps to Complete:

1. Read through the **Task Overview** and **System Assumptions** (available here: [Assumptions](#)).
2. Define System Requirements for **[OBJECTIVE]**:

- a. Identify key system requirements necessary to achieve **[OBJECTIVE]** within the system.
- b. Use the following [EARS](#) format for your response:
 - When <optional trigger>, the <system name> shall <system response>
- c. For each requirement, detail a **potential design solution** in bullet points.

Example:

- **Requirement:** *When a sudden obstacle is detected, the autonomous vehicle shall apply emergency braking to avoid a collision.*
 - **Potential Design Solutions:**
 - Implement LiDAR and camera-based object detection to identify obstacles in real time.
 - Develop an emergency braking algorithm that calculates safe stopping distances.
 - Integrate a redundant braking system to ensure functionality in case of sensor failure.
 - Conduct extensive simulations and real-world testing to validate emergency braking effectiveness.
3. Answer RL-Related Questions:
- a. After completing the requirements, you will receive an Excel sheet containing a set of questions assessing the RL & system design.
 - b. Provide **detailed responses**, following the provided example answer as a guide for the expected level of specificity:
 - Collision avoidance accuracy measures the percentage of successfully detected and avoided obstacles, with an acceptable range of $\geq 98\%$ based on autonomous flight performance benchmarks. Evasion precision is assessed using the Mean Absolute Error (MAE) of deviation from the optimal avoidance path, with an acceptable deviation of ≤ 0.5 meters to ensure precise maneuvering. These thresholds are determined through industry standards and empirical performance evaluations.
 - c. Some high-level questions (marked with an asterisk *) are broken down into sub-questions which may be fully addressed by responding to all sub-questions. If so, you may skip the high-level question as long as your responses to the sub-questions fully address it.
 - d. Some of your responses may overlap—this is okay! If responses overlap, you may **reference previous answers** (include the relevant ASK ID #) but you should still explain how the design choice applies to the current question.
 - e. If a question does not apply, respond with **N/A** and briefly explain why.
4. Review and Provide Feedback on Requirements:
- a. Based on your responses, a refined set of system requirements will be developed.
 - b. You will review these new requirements and provide feedback in a **brief interview**.

- c. During this session, you may be asked to **elaborate on some of your responses**.

Additional Notes

- You may use any available tools to assist with your task.
- However, you must be able to **explain and justify** your answers in a short meeting.
- Do not submit any responses you **cannot clearly explain**.
- You will **not** be implementing the system, but your responses should be **realistic and implementable** given sufficient time.